

Neutrosophic α^m -continuity

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Abstract: In this paper, we introduce and study a new class of neutrosophic closed set called neutrosophic α^m -closed set. In this respect, we introduce the concepts of neutrosophic α^m -continuous, strongly neutrosophic α^m continuous, neutrosophic α^m -irresolute and present their basic properties.

Keywords: Neutrosophic α^m -closed set, neutrosophic α^m -continuous, strongly neutrosophic α^m -continuous, neutrosophic α^m -irresolute.

1 Introduction

In 1965, Zadeh [21] studied the idea of fuzzy sets and its logic. Later, Chang [8] introduced the concept of fuzzy topological spaces. Atanassov [1] discussed the concepts of intuitionistic fuzzy set[[2],[3],[4]]. The concepts of strongly fuzzy continuous and fuzzy gc-irresolute are introduced by G. Balasubramanian and P. Sundaram [6]. The idea of α^m -closed in topological spaces was introduced by M. Mathew and R. Parimelazhagan[16]. He also introduced and investigated, α^m -continuous maps in topological spaces together with S. Jafari[17]. The concept of fuzzy α^m -continuous function was introduced by R. Dhavaseelan[13]. After the introduction of the concept of neutrosophy and neutrosophic set by F. Smarandache [[19], [20]], the concepts of neutrosophic crisp set and neutrosophic crisp topological space were introduced by A. A. Salama and S. A. Alblowi[18]. In this paper, a new class of neutrosophic closed set called neutrosophic α^m closed set is studied. Furthermore, the concepts of neutrosophic α^m -continuous, strongly neutrosophic α^m -continuous, neutrosophic α^m -irresolute are introduced and obtain some interesting properties. Throughout this paper neutrosophic topological spaces (briefly *NTS*) $(S_1, \xi_1), (S_2, \xi_2)$ and (S_3, ξ_3) will be replaced by S_1, S_2 and S_3 , respectively.

2 Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. [19] Let T, I, F be real standard or non standard subsets of $]0^-, 1^+[$, with $sup_T = t_{sup}, inf_T = t_{inf}$
 $sup_I = i_{sup}, inf_I = i_{inf}$
 $sup_F = f_{sup}, inf_F = f_{inf}$
 $n - sup = t_{sup} + i_{sup} + f_{sup}$
 $n - inf = t_{inf} + i_{inf} + f_{inf}$. T, I, F are neutrosophic components.

Definition 2.2. [19] Let S_1 be a non-empty fixed set. A neutrosophic set (briefly N -set) Λ is an object such that $\Lambda = \{\langle x, \mu_\Lambda(x), \sigma_\Lambda(x), \gamma_\Lambda(x) \rangle : x \in S_1\}$ where $\mu_\Lambda(x), \sigma_\Lambda(x)$ and $\gamma_\Lambda(x)$ which represents the degree of membership function (namely $\mu_\Lambda(x)$), the degree of indeterminacy (namely $\sigma_\Lambda(x)$) and the degree of non-membership (namely $\gamma_\Lambda(x)$) respectively of each element $x \in S_1$ to the set Λ .

Remark 2.3. [19]

- (1) An N -set $\Lambda = \{\langle x, \mu_\Lambda(x), \sigma_\Lambda(x), \Gamma_\Lambda(x) \rangle : x \in S_1\}$ can be identified to an ordered triple $\langle \mu_\Lambda, \sigma_\Lambda, \Gamma_\Lambda \rangle$ in $]0^-, 1^+[$ on S_1 .
- (2) In this paper, we use the symbol $\Lambda = \langle \mu_\Lambda, \sigma_\Lambda, \Gamma_\Lambda \rangle$ for the N -set $\Lambda = \{\langle x, \mu_\Lambda(x), \sigma_\Lambda(x), \Gamma_\Lambda(x) \rangle : x \in S_1\}$.

Definition 2.4. [18] Let $S_1 \neq \emptyset$ and the N -sets Λ and Γ be defined as $\Lambda = \{\langle x, \mu_\Lambda(x), \sigma_\Lambda(x), \Gamma_\Lambda(x) \rangle : x \in S_1\}$, $\Gamma = \{\langle x, \mu_\Gamma(x), \sigma_\Gamma(x), \Gamma_\Gamma(x) \rangle : x \in S_1\}$. Then

- (a) $\Lambda \subseteq \Gamma$ iff $\mu_\Lambda(x) \leq \mu_\Gamma(x), \sigma_\Lambda(x) \leq \sigma_\Gamma(x)$ and $\Gamma_\Lambda(x) \geq \Gamma_\Gamma(x)$ for all $x \in S_1$;
- (b) $\Lambda = \Gamma$ iff $\Lambda \subseteq \Gamma$ and $\Gamma \subseteq \Lambda$;
- (c) $\bar{\Lambda} = \{\langle x, \Gamma_\Lambda(x), \sigma_\Lambda(x), \mu_\Lambda(x) \rangle : x \in S_1\}$; [Complement of Λ]
- (d) $\Lambda \cap \Gamma = \{\langle x, \mu_\Lambda(x) \wedge \mu_\Gamma(x), \sigma_\Lambda(x) \wedge \sigma_\Gamma(x), \Gamma_\Lambda(x) \vee \Gamma_\Gamma(x) \rangle : x \in S_1\}$;
- (e) $\Lambda \cup \Gamma = \{\langle x, \mu_\Lambda(x) \vee \mu_\Gamma(x), \sigma_\Lambda(x) \vee \sigma_\Gamma(x), \Gamma_\Lambda(x) \wedge \Gamma_\Gamma(x) \rangle : x \in S_1\}$;
- (f) $[]\Lambda = \{\langle x, \mu_\Lambda(x), \sigma_\Lambda(x), 1 - \mu_\Lambda(x) \rangle : x \in S_1\}$;
- (g) $\langle \rangle\Lambda = \{\langle x, 1 - \Gamma_\Lambda(x), \sigma_\Lambda(x), \Gamma_\Lambda(x) \rangle : x \in S_1\}$.

Definition 2.5. [10] Let $\{\Lambda_i : i \in J\}$ be an arbitrary family of N -sets in S_1 . Then

- (a) $\bigcap \Lambda_i = \{\langle x, \wedge \mu_{\Lambda_i}(x), \wedge \sigma_{\Lambda_i}(x), \vee \Gamma_{\Lambda_i}(x) \rangle : x \in S_1\}$;
- (b) $\bigcup \Lambda_i = \{\langle x, \vee \mu_{\Lambda_i}(x), \vee \sigma_{\Lambda_i}(x), \wedge \Gamma_{\Lambda_i}(x) \rangle : x \in S_1\}$.

In order to develop NTS we need to introduce the N -sets 0_N and 1_N in S_1 as follows:

Definition 2.6. [10] $0_N = \{\langle x, 0, 0, 1 \rangle : x \in S_1\}$ and $1_N = \{\langle x, 1, 1, 0 \rangle : x \in S_1\}$.

Definition 2.7. [10] A neutrosophic topology (briefly N -topology) on $S_1 \neq \emptyset$ is a family ξ_1 of N -sets in S_1 satisfying the following axioms:

- (i) $0_N, 1_N \in \xi_1$,
- (ii) $G_1 \cap G_2 \in T$ for any $G_1, G_2 \in \xi_1$,
- (iii) $\cup G_i \in \xi_1$ for arbitrary family $\{G_i \mid i \in \Lambda\} \subseteq \xi_1$.

In this case the ordered pair (S_1, ξ_1) or simply S_1 is called an *NTS* and each N -set in ξ_1 is called a neutrosophic open set (briefly *N*-open set) . The complement $\bar{\Lambda}$ of an *N*-open set Λ in S_1 is called a neutrosophic closed set (briefly *N*-closed set) in S_1 .

Definition 2.8. [10] Let Λ be an *N*-set in an *NTS* S_1 . Then

$Nint(\Lambda) = \cup\{G \mid G \text{ is an } N\text{-open set in } S_1 \text{ and } G \subseteq \Lambda\}$ is called the neutrosophic interior (briefly *N*-interior) of Λ ;

$Ncl(\Lambda) = \cap\{G \mid G \text{ is an } N\text{-closed set in } S_1 \text{ and } G \supseteq \Lambda\}$ is called the neutrosophic closure (briefly *N-cl*) of Λ .

Definition 2.9. Let $S_1 \neq \emptyset$. If r, t, s be real standard or non standard subsets of $]0^-, 1^+[$ then the *N*-set $x_{r,t,s}$ is called a neutrosophic point(briefly *NP*)in S_1 given by

$$x_{r,t,s}(x_p) = \begin{cases} (r, t, s), & \text{if } x = x_p \\ (0, 0, 1), & \text{if } x \neq x_p \end{cases}$$

for $x_p \in S_1$ is called the support of $x_{r,t,s}$, where r denotes the degree of membership value, t denotes the degree of indeterminacy and s is the degree of non-membership value of $x_{r,t,s}$.

Now we shall define the image and preimage of *N*-sets. Let $S_1 \neq \emptyset$ and $S_2 \neq \emptyset$ and $\Omega : S_1 \rightarrow S_2$ be a map.

Definition 2.10. [10]

(a) If $\Gamma = \{\langle y, \mu_\Gamma(y), \sigma_\Gamma(y), \Gamma_\Gamma(y) \rangle : y \in S_2\}$ is an *N*-set in S_2 , then the pre-image of Γ under Ω , denoted by $\Omega^{-1}(\Gamma)$, is the *N*-set in S_1 defined by

$$\Omega^{-1}(\Gamma) = \{\langle x, \Omega^{-1}(\mu_\Gamma)(x), \Omega^{-1}(\sigma_\Gamma)(x), \Omega^{-1}(\Gamma_\Gamma)(x) \rangle : x \in S_1\}.$$

(b) If $\Lambda = \{\langle x, \mu_\Lambda(x), \sigma_\Lambda(x), \Gamma_\Lambda(x) \rangle : x \in S_1\}$ is an *N*-set in S_1 , then the image of Λ under Ω , denoted by $\Omega(\Lambda)$, is the *N*-set in S_2 defined by

$$\Omega(\Lambda) = \{\langle y, \Omega(\mu_\Lambda)(y), \Omega(\sigma_\Lambda)(y), (1 - \Omega(1 - \Gamma_\Lambda))(y) \rangle : y \in S_2\}. \text{ where}$$

$$\Omega(\mu_\Lambda)(y) = \begin{cases} \sup_{x \in \Omega^{-1}(y)} \mu_\Lambda(x), & \text{if } \Omega^{-1}(y) \neq \emptyset, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

$$\Omega(\sigma_\Lambda)(y) = \begin{cases} \sup_{x \in \Omega^{-1}(y)} \sigma_\Lambda(x), & \text{if } \Omega^{-1}(y) \neq \emptyset, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

$$(1 - \Omega(1 - \Gamma_\Lambda))(y) = \begin{cases} \inf_{x \in \Omega^{-1}(y)} \Gamma_\Lambda(x), & \text{if } \Omega^{-1}(y) \neq \emptyset, \\ 1, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

In what follows, we use the symbol $\Omega_-(\Gamma_\Lambda)$ for $1 - \Omega(1 - \Gamma_\Lambda)$.

Corollary 2.11. [10] Let $\Lambda, \Lambda_i (i \in J)$ be N -sets in S_1 , $\Gamma, \Gamma_i (i \in K)$ be N -sets in S_1 and $\Omega : S_1 \rightarrow S_2$ a function. Then

- (a) $\Lambda_1 \subseteq \Lambda_2 \Rightarrow \Omega(\Lambda_1) \subseteq \Omega(\Lambda_2)$,
- (b) $\Gamma_1 \subseteq \Gamma_2 \Rightarrow \Omega^{-1}(\Gamma_1) \subseteq \Omega^{-1}(\Gamma_2)$,
- (c) $\Lambda \subseteq \Omega^{-1}(\Omega(\Lambda))$ { If Ω is injective, then $\Lambda = \Omega^{-1}(\Omega(\Lambda))$ } ,
- (d) $\Omega(\Omega^{-1}(\Gamma)) \subseteq \Gamma$ { If Ω is surjective, then $\Omega(\Omega^{-1}(\Gamma)) = \Gamma$ } ,
- (e) $\Omega^{-1}(\bigcup \Gamma_j) = \bigcup \Omega^{-1}(\Gamma_j)$,
- (f) $\Omega^{-1}(\bigcap \Gamma_j) = \bigcap \Omega^{-1}(\Gamma_j)$,
- (g) $\Omega(\bigcup \Lambda_i) = \bigcup \Omega(\Lambda_i)$,
- (h) $\Omega(\bigcap \Lambda_i) \subseteq \bigcap \Omega(\Lambda_i)$ { If Ω is injective, then $\Omega(\bigcap \Lambda_i) = \bigcap \Omega(\Lambda_i)$ } ,
- (i) $\Omega^{-1}(1_N) = 1_N$,
- (j) $\Omega^{-1}(0_N) = 0_N$,
- (k) $\Omega(1_N) = 1_N$, if Ω is surjective
- (l) $\Omega(0_N) = 0_N$,
- (m) $\overline{\Omega(\Lambda)} \subseteq \Omega(\overline{\Lambda})$, if Ω is surjective,
- (n) $\Omega^{-1}(\overline{\Gamma}) = \overline{\Omega^{-1}(\Gamma)}$.

Definition 2.12. [11] An N -set Λ in an $NTS (S_1, \xi_1)$ is called

- 1) a neutrosophic semiopen set (briefly N -semiopen) if $\Lambda \subseteq Ncl(Nint(\Lambda))$.
- 2) a neutrosophic α open set (briefly $N\alpha$ -open set) if $\Lambda \subseteq Nint(Ncl(Nint(\Lambda)))$.
- 3) a neutrosophic preopen set (briefly N -preopen set) if $\Lambda \subseteq Nint(Ncl(\Lambda))$.
- 4) a neutrosophic regular open set (briefly N -regular open set) if $\Lambda = Nint(Ncl(\Lambda))$.
- 5) a neutrosophic semipre open or β open set (briefly $N\beta$ -open set) if $\Lambda \subseteq Ncl(Nint(Ncl(\Lambda)))$.

An N -set Λ is called a neutrosophic semiclosed set, neutrosophic α closed set, neutrosophic preclosed set, neutrosophic regular closed set and neutrosophic β closed set, respectively, if the complement of Λ is an N -semiopen set, $N\alpha$ -open set, N -preopen set, N -regular open set, and $N\beta$ -open set, respectively.

Definition 2.13. [10] Let (S_1, ξ_1) be an NTS . An N -set Λ in (S_1, ξ_1) is said to be a generalized neutrosophic closed set (briefly g - N -closed set) if $Ncl(\Lambda) \subseteq G$ whenever $\Lambda \subseteq G$ and G is an N -open set. The complement of a generalized neutrosophic closed set is called a generalized neutrosophic open set (briefly g - N -open set).

Definition 2.14. [10] Let (S_1, ξ_1) be an NTS and Λ be an N -set in S_1 . Then the neutrosophic generalized closure (briefly N - g - cl) and neutrosophic generalized interior (briefly N - g - Int) of Λ are defined by,

- (i) $NGcl(\Lambda) = \bigcap \{G: G \text{ is a } g\text{-}N\text{-closed set in } S_1 \text{ and } \Lambda \subseteq G\}$.
- (ii) $NGint(\Lambda) = \bigcup \{G: G \text{ is a } g\text{-}N\text{-open set in } S_1 \text{ and } \Lambda \supseteq G\}$.

3 Neutrosophic α^m continuous functions

Definition 3.1. An N -subset Λ of an $NTS (S_1, \xi_1)$ is called neutrosophic α^m -closed set (briefly $N\alpha^m$ -closed set) if $Nint(Ncl(\Lambda)) \subseteq U$ whenever $\Lambda \subseteq U$ and U is $N\alpha$ -open.

Definition 3.2. An N -subset λ of an $NTS (S_1, \xi_1)$ is called a neutrosophic αg -closed set (briefly $N\alpha g$ -closed set) if $\alpha Ncl(\lambda) \subseteq U$ whenever $\lambda \subseteq U$ and U is an $N\alpha$ -open set in S_1 .

Definition 3.3. An N -subset λ of an $NTS (S_1, \xi_1)$ is called a neutrosophic $g\alpha$ -closed set (briefly $Ng\alpha$ -closed set) if $\alpha Ncl(\Lambda) \subseteq U$ whenever $\Lambda \subseteq U$ and U is an N -open set in S_1 .

Remark 3.4. In an $NTS (S_1, \xi_1)$, the following statements are true:

- (i) Every N -closed set is an Ng -closed set.
- (ii) Every N -closed set is an $N\alpha$ -closed set.

Remark 3.5. In an $NTS (S_1, \xi_1)$, the following statements are true:

- (i) Every Ng -closed set is an $Ng\alpha$ -closed set.
- (ii) Every $N\alpha$ -closed set is an $N\alpha g$ -closed set.
- (iii) Every $N\alpha g$ -closed set is an $Ng\alpha$ -closed set.

Remark 3.6. In an $NTS (S_1, \xi_1)$, the following statements are true:

- (i) Every N -closed set is an $N\alpha^m$ -closed set.
- (ii) Every $N\alpha^m$ -closed set is an $N\alpha$ -closed set.
- (iii) Every $N\alpha^m$ -closed set is an $N\alpha g$ -closed set.
- (iv) Every $N\alpha^m$ -closed set is an $Ng\alpha$ -closed set.

Proof. (i) This follows directly from the definitions.

(ii) Let Λ be an $N\alpha^m$ -closed set in S_1 and U a N -open set such that $\Lambda \subseteq U$. Since every N -open set is an $N\alpha$ -open set and Λ is a $N\alpha^m$ -closed set, $Nint(Ncl(\Lambda)) \subseteq (Nint(Ncl(\Lambda))) \cup (Ncl(Nint(\Lambda))) \subseteq U$. Therefore, Λ is an $N\alpha$ -closed set in S_1 .

(iii) It is a consequence of (ii) and remark 3.5 (ii).

(iv) It is a consequence of (iii) and remark 3.5 (iii). □

Proposition 3.7. The intersection of an $N\alpha^m$ -closed set and an N -closed set is an $N\alpha^m$ -closed set.

Proof. Let Λ be an $N\alpha^m$ -closed set and Ψ an N -closed set. Since Λ is an $N\alpha^m$ -closed set, $Nint(Ncl(\Lambda)) \subseteq U$ whenever $\Lambda \subseteq U$, where U is an $N\alpha$ -open set. To show that $\Lambda \cap \Psi$ is an $N\alpha^m$ -closed set, it is enough to show that $Nint(Ncl(\Lambda \cap \Psi)) \subseteq U$ whenever $\Lambda \cap \Psi \subseteq U$, where U is an $N\alpha$ -open set. Let $M = S_1 - \Psi$. Then $\Lambda \subseteq U \cup M$. Since M is an N -open set, $U \cup M$ is an $N\alpha$ -open set and Λ is an $N\alpha^m$ -closed set, $Nint(Ncl(\Lambda)) \subseteq U \cup M$. Now, $Nint(Ncl(\Lambda \cap \Psi)) \subseteq Nint(Ncl(\Lambda)) \cap Nint(Ncl(\Psi)) \subseteq Nint(Ncl(\Lambda)) \cap \Psi \subseteq (U \cup M) \cap \Psi \subseteq (U \cap \Psi) \cup (M \cap \Psi) \subseteq (U \cap \Psi) \cup 0_N \subseteq U$. This implies that $\Lambda \cap \Psi$ is an $N\alpha^m$ -closed set. □

Figure 1: Implications of a neutrosophic α^m -closed set

Proposition 3.8. If Λ and Γ are two $N\alpha^m$ -closed sets in an $NTS (S_1, \xi_1)$, then $\Lambda \cap \Gamma$ is an $N\alpha^m$ -closed set in S_1 .

Proof. Let Λ and Γ be two $N\alpha^m$ -closed sets in an $NTS (S_1, \xi_1)$. Let U be a $N\alpha$ -open set in S_1 such that $\Lambda \cap \Gamma \subseteq U$. Now, $Nint(Ncl(\Lambda \cap \Gamma)) \subseteq Nint(Ncl(\Lambda)) \cap Nint(Ncl(\Gamma)) \subseteq U$. Hence $\Lambda \cap \Gamma$ is an $N\alpha^m$ -closed set. \square

Proposition 3.9. Every $N\alpha^m$ -closed set is $N\alpha$ -closed set.

The converse of the above Proposition 3.9 need not be true.

Example 3.10. Let $S_1 = \{a, b, c\}$. Define the N -subsets Λ and Γ as follows $\Lambda = \{x, (\frac{a}{0.7}, \frac{b}{0.6}, \frac{c}{0.5}), (\frac{a}{0.7}, \frac{b}{0.6}, \frac{c}{0.5}), (\frac{a}{0.3}, \frac{b}{0.4}, \frac{c}{0.5})\}$, $\Gamma = \{x, (\frac{a}{0.3}, \frac{b}{0.3}, \frac{c}{0.3}), (\frac{a}{0.3}, \frac{b}{0.3}, \frac{c}{0.3}), (\frac{a}{0.7}, \frac{b}{0.7}, \frac{c}{0.7})\}$. Then $\xi_1 = \{0_{S_1}, 1_{S_1}, \Lambda, \Gamma\}$ is an N -topology on S_1 . Clearly (S_1, ξ_1) is an NTS . Observe that the N -subset $\Sigma = \{x, (\frac{a}{0.3}, \frac{b}{0.6}, \frac{c}{0.5}), (\frac{a}{0.3}, \frac{b}{0.6}, \frac{c}{0.5}), (\frac{a}{0.7}, \frac{b}{0.4}, \frac{c}{0.5})\}$ is $N\alpha$ -closed but it is not $N\alpha^m$ -closed set.

Definition 3.11. Let (S_1, ξ_1) be an NTS and Λ an N -subset of S_1 . Then the neutrosophic α^m -interior (briefly $N\alpha^m-I$) and the neutrosophic $N\alpha^m$ -closure (briefly $N\alpha^m-cl$) of Λ are defined by,

$$\alpha^m Nint(\Lambda) = \cup\{U|U \text{ is } N\alpha^m\text{-open set in } S_1 \text{ and } \Lambda \supseteq U\}$$

$$\alpha^m Ncl(\Lambda) = \cap\{U|U \text{ is } N\alpha^m\text{-closed set in } S_1 \text{ and } \Lambda \subseteq U\}.$$

Proposition 3.12. If Λ is an $N\alpha^m$ -c-set and $\Lambda \subseteq \Gamma \subseteq Nint(Ncl(\Lambda))$, then Γ is $N\alpha^m$ -c-set.

Proof. Let Λ be an $N\alpha^m$ -c-set such that $\Lambda \subseteq \Gamma \subseteq Nint(Ncl(\Lambda))$. Let U be an $N\alpha$ -open set of S_1 such that $\Gamma \subseteq U$. Since Λ is $N\alpha^m$ -c-set, we have $Nint(Ncl(\Lambda)) \subseteq U$, whenever $\Lambda \subseteq U$. Since $\Lambda \subseteq \Gamma$ and $\Gamma \subseteq Nint(Ncl(\Lambda))$, then $Nint(Ncl(\Gamma)) \subseteq Nint(Ncl(Nint(Ncl(\Lambda)))) \subseteq Nint(Ncl(\Lambda)) \subseteq U$. Therefore $Nint(Ncl(\Gamma)) \subseteq U$. Hence Γ is an $N\alpha^m$ -c-set in S_1 . \square

Remark 3.13. The union of two $N\alpha^m$ -c-sets need not be an $N\alpha^m$ -c-set.

Remark 3.14. The following are the implications of an $N\alpha^m$ -c-set and the reverses are not true.

Definition 3.15. Let (S_1, ξ_1) and (S_2, ξ_2) be any two *NTS*.

- 1) A map $\Omega : (S_1, \xi_1) \rightarrow (S_2, \xi_2)$ is called neutrosophic α^m -continuous (briefly $N\alpha^m$ -cont) if the inverse image of every N -closed set in (S_2, ξ_2) is $N\alpha^m$ - c -set in (S_1, ξ_1) .
Equivalently if the inverse image of every N -open set in (S_2, ξ_2) is $N\alpha^m$ -open set in (S_1, ξ_1) .
- 2) A map $\Omega : (S_1, \xi_1) \rightarrow (S_2, \xi_2)$ is called neutrosophic α^m -irresolute (briefly $N\alpha^m$ -I) if the inverse image of every $N\alpha^m$ - c -set in (S_2, ξ_2) is $N\alpha^m$ - c -set in (S_1, ξ_1) .
Equivalently if the inverse image of every $N\alpha^m$ -open set in (S_2, ξ_2) is $N\alpha^m$ -open set in (S_1, ξ_1) .
- 3) A map $\Omega : (S_1, \xi_1) \rightarrow (S_2, \xi_2)$ is called strongly neutrosophic α^m -continuous (briefly $SN\alpha^m$ -cont) if the inverse image of every $N\alpha^m$ - c -set in (S_2, ξ_2) is N -closed set in (S_1, ξ_1) .
Equivalently if the inverse image of every $N\alpha^m$ -open set in (S_2, ξ_2) is N -open set in (S_1, ξ_1) .

Proposition 3.16. Let (S_1, ξ_1) and (S_2, ξ_2) be any two *NTS*. If $\Omega : (S_1, \xi_1) \rightarrow (S_2, \xi_2)$ is *NC*, then it is $N\alpha^m$ -cont.

Proof. Let Λ be any N -closed set in (S_2, ξ_2) . Since f is *NC*, $\Omega^{-1}(\Lambda)$ is N -closed in (S_1, ξ_1) . Since every N -closed set is $N\alpha^m$ - c -set, $\Omega^{-1}(\Lambda)$ is $N\alpha^m$ - c -set in (S_1, ξ_1) . Therefore Ω is $N\alpha^m$ -cont. □

The converse of Proposition 3.16 need not be true as it is shown in the following example.

Example 3.17. Let $S_1 = \{a, b, c\}$ and $S_2 = \{a, b, c\}$. Define N -subsets E, F, G and D as follows
 $E = \{x, (\frac{a}{0.3}, \frac{b}{0.5}, \frac{c}{0.3}), (\frac{a}{0.3}, \frac{b}{0.5}, \frac{c}{0.3}), (\frac{a}{0.7}, \frac{b}{0.5}, \frac{c}{0.7})\}$, $F = \{x, (\frac{a}{0.4}, \frac{b}{0.5}, \frac{c}{0.4}), (\frac{a}{0.4}, \frac{b}{0.5}, \frac{c}{0.4}), (\frac{a}{0.6}, \frac{b}{0.5}, \frac{c}{0.6})\}$, $G = \{x, (\frac{a}{0.4}, \frac{b}{0.4}, \frac{c}{0.5}), (\frac{a}{0.4}, \frac{b}{0.4}, \frac{c}{0.5}), (\frac{a}{0.6}, \frac{b}{0.6}, \frac{c}{0.5})\}$, and $D = \{x, (\frac{a}{0.3}, \frac{b}{0.3}, \frac{c}{0.5}), (\frac{a}{0.3}, \frac{b}{0.3}, \frac{c}{0.5}), (\frac{a}{0.7}, \frac{b}{0.7}, \frac{c}{0.5})\}$. Then the family $\xi_1 = \{0_{S_1}, 1_{S_1}, E, F\}$ is an *NT* on S_1 and $\xi_2 = \{0_{S_2}, 1_{S_2}, G, D\}$ is an *NT* on S_2 . Thus (S_1, ξ_1) and (S_2, ξ_2) are *NTS*. Define $\Omega : (S_1, \xi_1) \rightarrow (S_2, \xi_2)$ as $\Omega(a) = a, \Omega(b) = c, \Omega(c) = b$. Clearly Ω is $N\alpha^m$ -cont but Ω is not *NC* since $\Omega^{-1}(D) \notin \xi_1$ for $D \in \xi_2$.

Proposition 3.18. Let (S_1, ξ_1) and (S_2, ξ_2) be any two neutrosophic *NTS*. If $\Omega : (S_1, \xi_1) \rightarrow (S_2, \xi_2)$ is $N\alpha^m$ -I, then it is $N\alpha^m$ -cont.

Proof. Let Λ be an N -closed set in (S_2, ξ_2) . Since every N -closed set is $N\alpha^m$ - c -set, Λ is $N\alpha^m$ - c -set in S_2 . Since Ω is $N\alpha^m$ -I, $\Omega^{-1}(\Lambda)$ is $N\alpha^m$ - c -set in (S_1, ξ_1) . Therefore Ω is $N\alpha^m$ -cont. □

The converse of Proposition 3.18 need not be true.

Example 3.19. Let $S_1 = \{a, b, c\}$. Define the N -subsets E, F and G as follows
 $E = \{x, (\frac{a}{0.4}, \frac{b}{0.5}, \frac{c}{0.4}), (\frac{a}{0.4}, \frac{b}{0.5}, \frac{c}{0.4}), (\frac{a}{0.6}, \frac{b}{0.5}, \frac{c}{0.6})\}$, $F = \{x, (\frac{a}{0.6}, \frac{b}{0.6}, \frac{c}{0.5}), (\frac{a}{0.6}, \frac{b}{0.6}, \frac{c}{0.5}), (\frac{a}{0.4}, \frac{b}{0.4}, \frac{c}{0.5})\}$ and $G = \{x, (\frac{a}{0.5}, \frac{b}{0.4}, \frac{c}{0.7}), (\frac{a}{0.5}, \frac{b}{0.4}, \frac{c}{0.7}), (\frac{a}{0.5}, \frac{b}{0.6}, \frac{c}{0.3})\}$. Then $\xi_1 = \{0_{S_1}, 1_{S_1}, E, F\}$ and $\xi_2 = \{0_{S_1}, 1_{S_1}, G\}$ are N -topologies on S_1 . Define $\Omega : (S_1, \xi_1) \rightarrow (S_1, \xi_2)$ as follows $\Omega(a) = b, \Omega(b) = a, \Omega(c) = c$. Observe that Ω is $N\alpha^m$ -continuous. But Ω is not $N\alpha^m$ -I. Since $D = \{x, (\frac{a}{0.5}, \frac{b}{0.4}, \frac{c}{0.2}), (\frac{a}{0.5}, \frac{b}{0.4}, \frac{c}{0.2}), (\frac{a}{0.5}, \frac{b}{0.6}, \frac{c}{0.8})\}$ is $N\alpha^m$ - c -set in (S_1, ξ_2) , $\Omega^{-1}(D)$ is not $N\alpha$ - c -set in (S_1, ξ_1) .

Proposition 3.20. Let (S_1, ξ_1) and (S_2, ξ_2) be any two *NTS*. If $\Omega : (S_1, \xi_1) \rightarrow (S_2, \xi_2)$ is $SN\alpha^m$ -I, then it is *NC*.

Proof. Let Λ be an N -closed set in (S_2, ξ_2) . Since every N -closed set is $N\alpha^m$ - c -set. Since Ω is $SN\alpha^m$ -cont, $\Omega^{-1}(\Lambda)$ is N -closed set in (S_1, ξ_1) . Therefore Ω is *NC*. □

The converse of Proposition 3.20 need not be true.

Example 3.21. Let $S_1 = \{a, b, c\}$. Define the N -subsets E, F and G as follows

$E = \{x, (\frac{a}{0.1}, \frac{b}{0.1}, \frac{c}{0.1}), (\frac{a}{0.1}, \frac{b}{0.1}, \frac{c}{0.1}), (\frac{a}{0.9}, \frac{b}{0.9}, \frac{c}{0.9})\}$, $F = \{x, (\frac{a}{0.1}, \frac{b}{0.1}, \frac{c}{0}), (\frac{a}{0.1}, \frac{b}{0.1}, \frac{c}{0}), (\frac{a}{0.9}, \frac{b}{0.9}, \frac{c}{1})\}$ and $G = \{x, (\frac{a}{0.1}, \frac{b}{0}, \frac{c}{0.1}), (\frac{a}{0.1}, \frac{b}{0}, \frac{c}{0.1}), (\frac{a}{0.9}, \frac{b}{1}, \frac{c}{0.9})\}$. Then $\xi_1 = \{0_{S_1}, 1_{S_1}, E, F\}$ and $\xi_2 = \{0_{S_1}, 1_{S_1}, G\}$ are N -topologies on S_1 . Define $\Omega(S_1, \xi_1) \rightarrow (S_1, \xi_2)$ as follows $\Omega(a) = \Omega(b) = a, \Omega(c) = c$. Ω is NC but Ω is not $SN\alpha^m$ -cont. Since $D = \{x, (\frac{a}{0.05}, \frac{b}{0}, \frac{c}{0.1}), (\frac{a}{0.05}, \frac{b}{0}, \frac{c}{0.1}), (\frac{a}{0.95}, \frac{b}{1}, \frac{c}{0.9})\}$ is $N\alpha^m$ - c -set in (S_1, ξ_2) , $\Omega^{-1}(D)$ is not N -closed set in (S_1, ξ_1) .

Proposition 3.22. Let $(S_1, \xi_1), (S_2, \xi_2)$ and (S_3, ξ_3) be any three NTS . Suppose $\Omega : (S_1, \xi_1) \rightarrow (S_2, \xi_2)$, $\Xi : (S_2, \xi_2) \rightarrow (S_3, \xi_3)$ are maps. Assume Ω is $N\alpha^m$ - I and Ξ is $N\alpha^m$ -cont, then $\Xi \circ \Omega$ is $N\alpha^m$ -cont.

Proof. Let Λ be an N -closed set in (S_3, ξ_3) . Since Ξ is $N\alpha^m$ -cont, $\Xi^{-1}(\Lambda)$ is $N\alpha^m$ - c -set in (S_2, ξ_2) . Since Ω is $N\alpha^m$ - I , $\Omega^{-1}(\Xi^{-1}(\Lambda))$ is $N\alpha^m$ -closed in (S_1, ξ_1) . Thus $\Xi \circ \Omega$ is $N\alpha^m$ -cont. \square

Proposition 3.23. Let $(S_1, \xi_1), (S_2, \xi_2)$ and (S_3, ξ_3) be any three NTS . Let $\Omega : (S_1, \xi_1) \rightarrow (S_2, \xi_2)$ and $\Xi : (S_2, \xi_2) \rightarrow (S_3, \xi_3)$ be maps such that Ω is $SN\alpha^m$ -cont and Ξ is $N\alpha^m$ -cont, then $\Xi \circ \Omega$ is NC .

Proof. Let Λ be an N - c -set in (S_3, ξ_3) . Since Ξ is $N\alpha^m$ -cont, $\Xi^{-1}(\Lambda)$ is $N\alpha^m$ - c -set in (S_2, ξ_2) . Moreover, since Ω is $SN\alpha^m$ -cont, $\Omega^{-1}(\Xi^{-1}(\Lambda))$ is N -closed in (S_1, ξ_1) . Thus $\Xi \circ \Omega$ is NC . \square

Proposition 3.24. Let $(S_1, \xi_1), (S_2, \xi_2)$ and (S_3, ξ_3) be any three NTS . Let $\Omega : (S_1, \xi_1) \rightarrow (S_2, \xi_2)$ and $\Xi : (S_2, \xi_2) \rightarrow (S_3, \xi_3)$ be two maps. Assume Ω and Ξ are $N\alpha^m$ - I , then $\Xi \circ \Omega$ is $N\alpha^m$ - I .

Proof. Let Λ be an $N\alpha^m$ - c -set in (S_3, ξ_3) . Since Ξ is $N\alpha^m$ - I , $\Xi^{-1}(\Lambda)$ is $N\alpha^m$ - c -set in (S_2, ξ_2) . Since Ω is $N\alpha^m$ - I , $\Omega^{-1}(\Xi^{-1}(\Lambda))$ is an $N\alpha^m$ - c -set in (S_1, ξ_1) . Thus $\Xi \circ \Omega$ is $N\alpha^m$ - I . \square

4 Conclusions

In this paper, a new class of neutrosophic closed set called neutrosophic α^m closed set is introduced and studied. Furthermore, the basic properties of neutrosophic α^m -continuity are presented with some examples.

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